

FOUNDATIONS OF LEARNING ENGLISH MYTHOLOGY TO ANALYZE

L.CARROLL'S WORKS

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Annotation. *This article highlights the role of English mythology in literary, cultural and language teaching, and analyzes L.Cerroll's works, such as "Alice in wonderland" and "Through the looking-glass" based on modern approaches. The study examines the possibilities of forming students' language competence, intercultural perception and literary thinking based on mythological sources such as "Beowulf", the legends of King Arthur, and Celtic folklore. The effectiveness of using such methods as contextual reading, dramatization, visual methods, comparative analysis and creative expression in teaching mythology is substantiated. The topic is of particular relevance at a time when interest in learning a foreign language is growing among Uzbek students.*

Keywords: *English mythology, Beowulf, myth, dramatization, methodology, intercultural thinking, language competence, cultural context.*

INTRODUCTION

Mythology is an important factor in the thinking, historical memory and artistic worldview of a people. Each people understands and describes the world through its own mythological system. English mythology was also formed over many centuries on the basis of the oral creativity of the Celtic, Saxon, Norman and Anglo-Saxon peoples, and played an important role in the formation of today's English language and literature. This mythology is mainly transmitted through epics, epics, legends, legendary images and symbols, reflecting the worldview, moral values and historical memory of ancient society.

One of the most famous examples of English mythology is the epic poem "Beowulf", written in Old English, which was created in the 8th-9th centuries. The work glorifies wild creatures, courage, loyalty and endurance in the face of death. In it, the main character Beowulf fights Grendel and a dragon. This epic illuminates the concept of heroism, personal qualities and religious and philosophical views in ancient Anglo-Saxon society. "Beowulf" is distinguished by its poetic style, metaphorical language and abundance of mythological images. In addition, the legends of King Arthur form another important layer of English mythology. These legends illuminate the concepts of medieval chivalric morality, truth, glory and self-sacrifice through such symbols as Arthur, his loyal knights, the wizard Merlin, the mysterious island of Avalon and the legendary sword Excalibur. These narratives developed on the basis of historical and artistic elements in the works of writers such as William Malmesbury and Geoffrey of Monmouth.

The mythological layer also plays an important role in modern English literature. In particular, J.R.R. Tolkien created a completely artificial mythological system in his "The Lord of the Rings" trilogy and "The Silmarillion". He developed the concept of a new world - Middle-earth, inspired by the epic poem Beowulf and Celtic-mythical elements.

Similarly, C.S. Lewis's "The Chronicles of Narnia" and J.K. Rowling's "Harry Potter" series are also based on English mythological images, characters and plot construction.

Through these works, students learn how the mythological basis develops in modern fantasy literature in a changing and harmonious way.

Today, learning English requires not only grammatical and phonetic competence, but also cultural knowledge, contextual understanding and historical-philosophical foundations. English mythology serves as a rich educational resource in this regard. Through its teaching, intercultural competence is formed in students, the attitude towards the language being studied is deepened, and creative thinking is developed. Therefore, the use of English mythology materials in teaching English language and literature, especially at the university level, is of great pedagogical importance in forming an approach based on the integration of language and culture.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The article uses several methodological approaches to identify ways to effectively teach English mythology to students. Each method was selected in accordance with the literary, linguistic and pedagogical goals of the study and tested in practice. The following methods formed the main areas of scientific research:

- Theoretical-analytical method: In order to identify the formation, main sources, literary images and historical development of English mythology, existing literary, philological and pedagogical sources were studied in depth. Content analysis was carried out based on the stories of Beowulf, King Arthur's legends, Celtic folklore, Merlin and Avalon.

- Methodological observation and didactic experiment: In practical classes with students, such activities as dramatization, textual discussion, lexical-semantic analysis, role-playing, and working with visual materials were organized based on texts related to English mythology. In the process, students' activity, creative approach and level of thinking in cultural context were assessed.

- Comparative-analytical method: Similarities and differences between English mythology and Uzbek mythology, the system of heroes, plots and symbols were analyzed. For example, the images of "Beowulf" and "Alpomish", "Arthur" and "Rustam" were studied in comparison. Using this method, the possibility of developing students' intercultural thinking was analyzed.

- Interactive and innovative approaches: Using modern teaching technologies - visual presentations, multimedia tools, QR-tests, interactive platforms (Kahoot, Quizlet), students' interest in the lesson and the effectiveness of mastering language materials in context were increased. This approach served not only to master the language, but also to form a literary aesthetic taste in students.

- Analysis of creative expression and written exercises: Students completed tasks such as writing a new myth based on English mythology, writing an alternative ending to an existing story, and keeping a diary on behalf of a hero. Through these exercises, their language structure, cultural awareness, image creation, and stylistic analysis skills were observed.

These methods serve to ensure a deeper, culturally informed, and active study of English mythology by the student, based on the harmony of different approaches.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The research and observations conducted based on the above methods revealed the following practical results:

- Development of intercultural thinking: In the process of studying English mythology, students learned to assimilate images and concepts specific to other cultures, as well as compare

them with their own national values. Through this, their level of intercultural thinking was significantly developed. For example, through a comparative analysis of the images of Beowulf and Alpomish, students understood universal heroic archetypes.

- Deepening of language competence: As a result of lexical-semantic analysis, dramatic exercises and text-based discussions, students mastered language units in context. In particular, when concepts such as “grail”, “chivalry”, “oath”, “quest”, “sorcerer”, “destiny” were explained on a cultural basis, their level of semantic fullness of understanding increased.

- Formation of creative and critical thinking skills: By writing new myths, creating alternative endings to existing fairy tales, and writing texts on behalf of characters, students mastered creative thinking, figurative expression, and analytical thinking. This had a positive impact on the development of their written and oral speech.

- Increased motivation and engagement: Students who participated in lessons using interactive technologies (visual presentations, dramatization, tests, and games) reported greater participation than in traditional lessons. This contributed to an increase in interest in the English language.

- Development of aesthetic taste and literary thinking: Through the artistic depiction of English mythological characters, their expression in language, plot complexity, and the system of symbols, students acquired the skills of aesthetic evaluation, understanding, and interpretation of artistic means.

- Effectiveness of integrative approaches: The integration of such areas as literature, history, culture, philosophy into the language learning process has expanded students' opportunities for complex thinking, contextual learning, generalization, and evaluation.

These results prove the effectiveness of using English mythology in education as a tool for developing not only linguistic, but also cultural, creative, and intellectual potential.

The results presented above show that using English mythology as a tool for teaching English meets the requirements of modern education. Working with mythological materials, especially at the university level, not only increases students' interest in language, culture, and literature, but also serves as an important factor in forming their thinking culture and aesthetic taste.

Students' active participation in lessons, their interest in dramatized activities, and freedom to express their opinions - all this confirms the high didactic potential of mythology in teaching. In particular, when conducting analytical work based on the epic poem Beowulf, students begin to understand the connection between the ancient worldview and the modern approach by studying the semantic layers of the image of the epic hero. This develops analytical thinking, historical thinking, and semantic coherence in them. Also, when analyzing the similarities and differences between “Merlin” and wise heroes of Uzbek folk tales (for example, Gijduvon Piri or Qaravoy) through an intercultural comparative approach, students were able to form a cultural mindset based on multi-layered images. With the help of these analyses, a desire to understand not only a foreign language, but also their own national culture arises. Another aspect that was paid attention to in the discussion process is related to the interpretation of metaphors and symbols in English mythology in translation. In many cases, it is required to find semantic equivalents suitable for the Uzbek language of such images and interpret them culturally correctly. This, in turn, requires cultural competence from the teacher, along with linguistic knowledge.

Also, from the point of view of teaching methodology, classes organized on the basis of English mythology are proving to be an effective tool for attracting students to the lesson, encouraging them to be active, and developing group work skills. By preparing scenes based on myths and reviving various characters, students not only activate their English speech, but also have the opportunity to test their dramatic skills. This serves as an important stage in bringing literary education to a vital and interactive form. Based on the observations and analyses conducted, it can be said that teaching English mythology to students has proven to be a powerful tool that enriches curricula and serves to harmoniously master language and culture. It is not only a language teaching tool, but also helps students to think independently, communicate with people in many spheres.

CONCLUSION

This study has shown that teaching English mythology is an effective tool not only for acquiring linguistic knowledge, but also for developing cultural, aesthetic and literary thinking.

Lessons based on mythological texts, in particular, the epic poem "Beowulf", the legends of King Arthur and Celtic legends, have shown that they enhance students' thinking skills, cultural awareness and creative approach. The results of the study revealed the enormous didactic potential of English mythology in the process of learning a foreign language at the university level in the formation of intercultural competence, instilling aesthetic taste, strengthening textual skills, developing dramatic expression and comparative analysis. Through these methods, language learning becomes not just about memorizing words or mastering grammar, but also a complex learning process enriched with personal reflection, literary observation and cultural understanding.

The theoretical-analytical, comparative, dramatic, interactive and creative approaches used in the article made it possible to form a methodological model of teaching mythology that meets modern requirements. In particular, the increased activity of students in the lesson, interest in assignments and independent creativity indicators showed the effectiveness of these methods. In conclusion, the educational process based on English mythology corresponds to the culturally based integrative model of language teaching. It ensures the mastery of not only the structure of a foreign language, but also its cultural semantic layers. This brings the approach to language learning in modern education to a qualitatively new level.

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